

Today's meaning of aikido principles

Greet De Baets | Ghent University | MULTIPLES Research Centre

Interview Invitation

My name is Greet De Baets, I teach business communication skills at the University of Ghent (Belgium) and I am a researcher. I am conducting academic/doctoral research on the meaning of aikido principles. By the way, I practise aikido.

The purpose of an interview with you is to learn what you consider to be principles of aikido on and off the mat. It is important to know this from you, an expert in aikido, in your country or region and in this day and age. The interview will take approximately one hour. If the distance between us is too big, we can use Skype or another online video tool.

You can pull out of the research participation, without any explanation:

- before we meet for the interview;
- during the interview;
- after the interview;
- before the information has been processed and prepared for publication.

The interview consists of four groups of questions:

- a. What is your martial biography and lineage?
- b. What do you consider to be the main aikido principles?
- c. How do you use/perceive aikido off the mat?
- d. Is aikido unique? Why?

The interview will be anonymous, the research will however mention the aikido grade, aikido lineage, nationality, current country and town, and gender.

Research Background

Aikido is being taught all over the world. The input of aikido senseis from all over the world will show differences and similarities in the way aikido is perceived, understood, practised and taught.

This study into aikido principles serves as a benchmark to determine which aikido principles are valuable outside the dojo. The overall PhD research will ultimately focus on aikido as a model for teaching intercultural business communication skills. Teaching intercultural competencies, or any other skill, effectively is a challenge. This research, therefore, will explore the effectiveness and efficiency of intercultural training based on the principles of aikido. It uses interviews, questionnaires and an experiment which compares aikido-based intercultural training and non-aikido-based intercultural training.

Greet DE BAETS (Ms)

Doctoral Researcher | MULTIPLES Research Centre for Multilingual Practices and Language Learning in Society
Academic Assistant | Department of translation, interpreting and communication

Ghent University, Belgium

+ 32 474 71 48 00

greet.debaets@ugent.be

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/greetdebaets/>

